

THE INFLUENCE OF VITAMIN-C ON THE INACTIVATION OF ENZYMES BY ULTRAVIOLET LIGHT.

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Liver phosphatase, sweet potato amylase and pepsin are inactivated when their solutions are exposed to ultraviolet radiation, and vitamin-C is found to protect the enzymes against the inactivation.

It is well known that ultraviolet radiation influences enzyme action. In general, enzymes are inactivated by the radiation. Enzymes and vitamin-C occur together in all the living tissues of plants and animals. It would, therefore, be of interest to know whether vitamin-C has any influence on the destructive action of ultraviolet radiation on enzymes. The present paper describes some preliminary investigation on the influence of vitamin-C on the inactivation of liver phosphatase, sweet potato amylase and pepsin by ultraviolet light.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Liver phosphatase and sweet potato amylase were prepared according to the methods previously described by Giri (*Biochem. J.*, 1939, 33, 309; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 339), and the procedure for the determination of the activity of the phosphatase and amylase was the same as described in previous publications. In the present investigation pepsin (B.D.H.) was used.

The enzyme solutions (phosphatase and amylase) were mixed with either glycine or acetate buffer of known p_H , and equal amounts of the solutions were pipetted into petri dishes (9.2 cm. diam.). To one of the samples known amount of vitamin-C was added, and the solutions were exposed to the unfiltered ultraviolet radiation. Two other samples of the solution, prepared under exactly similar conditions, were kept without exposure to ultraviolet light. The irradiations were made with the help of a quartz mercury vapour lamp (Hanovia, 220 volt D.C.) at a distance of about 19-20 cm. from the arc. To prevent a rise in temperature of the solutions an electric fan was kept running near the lamp. At stated intervals of time aliquots were removed for the estimation of the phosphatase and amylase activities and for the determination of vitamin-C by the usual dye method.

Liver Phosphatase.

Acetone-treated sheep's liver powder (20 g.), prepared according to the method described by Giri (*loc. cit.*), were extracted with 100 c.c. of water for 2 days in presence of toluene and filtered. The clear yellow filtrate was dialysed in collodion bags and centrifuged. After dialysis the extract was used for the experiment.

The experimental solutions were adjusted to p_H 5.0 and 8.5 by the addition of $M/5$ -acetate and $M/10$ -glycine buffer respectively. The compositions of the mixtures were as follows :

$$p_H = 8.5$$

Expt. soln.	Enzyme extract	Glycine buffer p_H 8.5	
A.	5 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	2 c.c. vitamin-C (5 mg.)
B.	"	"	2 c.c. water
C.	"	"	2 c.c. vitamin-C (5 mg.)
D.	"	"	2 c.c. water

The solutions A and B were exposed to ultraviolet light for 30 minutes, while the solutions C and D were kept for the same period at 37° in an incubator and the activities determined. The results are presented in Table I A.

$$p_H = 5.0$$

Expt. soln.	Enzyme soln.	$M/5$ -Acetate buffer	
A.	40 c.c.	10 c.c.	10 mg. vitamin C.
B.	"	"	Without vitamin

The experimental solutions A and B were exposed to ultraviolet light and the activities were determined at stated intervals of time.

The composition of the reaction mixture used for the estimation of the phosphatase activity was as follows :

$$\text{Temperature} = 37^\circ \pm 0.1$$

$M/10$ -Glycine buffer (p_H 8.9)	...	20 c.c.	Enzyme extract	...	...	10
2% Sodium β -glycerophosphate	...	10	Water	...	...	5
0.1 M - $MgCl_2$	...	5	Total volume	...	...	30

10 C.c. of the reaction mixture were used for the estimation of inorganic phosphorus by the method of Fiske and Subbarow (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1925, 66, 375). The results are shown in Table IA.

It appears from Table I that vitamin-C exerts protective action against the destruction of the phosphatase by ultraviolet light. The results in Table I and II show that the vitamin protects the enzyme from inactivation by ultraviolet light at both the acid and alkaline p_H . The loss of vitamin-C during the period of exposure at p_H 5.0 is very little, and the activity of the enzyme is, therefore, completely protected from inactivation at the acid p_H .

TABLE I.

Influence of vitamin-C on the inactivation of liver phosphatase by ultraviolet light.

A. At p_H 8.5. Activity in mg. p. in 10 c.c. of reaction mixture.			B. At p_H 5.0. Activity in mg. p. in 10 c.c. of reaction mixture				
Expt. Soln.	Time of hydrolysis		Exposed for	Duration of hydrolysis.			
	2 hrs.	3 hrs.		+ vitamin C.		without vitamin C.	
				2 hrs.	15 hrs.	2 hrs.	15 hrs.
A. Phosphatase + vitamin-C exposed to ultraviolet light	0.250	0.333	0 min.	0.143	0.730	0.143	0.730
B Phosphatase exposed to ultraviolet light	0.108	0.130	10	0.143	0.730	0.100	0.570
			20	0.133	0.730	0.091	0.533
C. Phosphatase + vitamin-C kept at 37°	0.347	0.444	30	0.133	0.730	0.083	0.421
D. Phosphatase kept at 37°	0.381	0.500	Destruction of vitamin-C in the exptl. soln. A [[vitamin-C in the total vol. of the mixture]				
			0 min.	10.0 mg.			
			10	10.0			
			20	9.4			
			30	9.1			

Amylase.

The amylase was prepared from sweet potato according to the method described by Giri (*loc. cit.*). Fresh tubers were minced and dried in the

sun. The sun-dried material was ground to a fine powder. 100 G. of the dry powdered meal were extracted with 400 c.c. of water for about 12 hours in presence of toluene and filtered. The filtrate after dialysis for two days in collodion bags was used for the experiment.

Experimental solutions :

- A. 25 c.c. of *N/5*-acetate buffer (pH 5.0)
30 c.c. of enzyme extract.
- B. 25 c.c. of *N/5*-acetate buffer (pH 5.0)
30 c.c. enzyme extract.
10 mg. of vitamin-C.

The solutions were exposed to ultra-violet light in petridishes of 9.0 cm. diameter, at a distance of 19.5 cm. from the arc. The temperature of the solution varied between 16-18°. At known intervals of time 10 c.c. were removed for the determination of the activity of the amylase.

The composition of the reaction mixture was as follows :

- 20 c.c. *M/5* acetate buffer (pH 5.6) = 10 c.c.
20 c.c. 2% soluble starch (Merck) soln. = 20
10 c.c. Amylase soln.
Temp. = 37°.

The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II.

Influence of vitamin-C on the inactivation of sweet potato amylase.

Exposed to ultraviolet,	Amylase activity* after 1 hour's hydrolysis at 37° ± 0.1.		Exposed to ultraviolet.	Amylase activity* after 1 hour's hydrolysis at 37° ± 0.1.	
	With vitamin-C.	Without vitamin-C.		With vitamin-C.	Without vitamin-C.
0 min.	165	215	60	165	173
30	165	201	120	161	149

The results show that as in the case of phosphatase, the sweet potato amylase is inactivated when the aqueous solution containing the enzyme is exposed to ultraviolet light. Vitamin-C protects the enzyme from the inactivation. The results also show that vitamin-C inhibits the activity of the amylase. It is found that the activity of the enzyme in presence of vitamin-C is lower than that of the enzyme in its absence. This is in conformity with the findings of Hanes (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, 29, 2588), who showed that β -amylase, prepared from barley, is inhibited by the vitamin. Although the vitamin exerts inhibiting action on the activity of the amylase, it protects the enzyme from inactivation by ultra-violet light.

* Expressed in mg. of maltose formed in the total volume of the reaction mixture

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Pepsin.—0.2% Pepsin (40 c.c.), dissolved in $N/6\text{-HCl}$, was exposed to ultraviolet light in petri dishes of 9 cm. diameter. The distance between the lamp and the solutions was 9 cm. One of the solutions contained 10 mg. of vitamin-C. The activity of the pepsin was determined before and after exposure, by formal titration of the casein solutions treated with the enzyme.

The reaction mixture contained 3% casein adjusted to $pH\ 1.5$. The total volume of the reaction mixture together with the enzyme amounted to 20 c.c. The digestion was carried at 37° for 30 minutes. The results are shown in Table III.

TABLE III.

Influence of vitamin C on the inactivation of pepsin by ultraviolet light

Exposed for	Activity of pepsin expressed in c.c. of $N/20\text{-NaOH}$.	
	With vitamin-C.	Without vitamin-C.
0 hr.	4.0	4.0
2	3.8	0.4

The results show that vitamin C protects pepsin from inactivation by ultra-violet light.

CONCLUSION.

The results clearly indicate that vitamin-C exerts protective action on liver phosphatase, amylase and pepsin_r against the inactivation by ultraviolet radiation. The protective action on liver phosphatase is exerted at both the acid and alkaline pH . The mechanism underlying the protective action of vitamin-C remains to be elucidated. The discovery of such protective agents like vitamin-C which are distributed in all the tissues of plants and animals would be of great significance, as the presence of such substances would render the ultraviolet light less harmful to enzyme systems, whose activity is kept in tact under the influence of the vitamin.

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